

Development of Speech in Preschool Children through Constructive Methods

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Abstract: *This paper examines the Build and Tell method as an effective tool for developing speech skills in preschool children. The study provides an analysis of the influence of constructive methods on various aspects of speech development, including expanding vocabulary, developing coherence of speech and logical presentation. The paper analyzes the results of an empirical study conducted in a preschool educational organization, where the method was adapted for age groups from 3 to 7 years. The main advantages and disadvantages of the method are presented, and its pedagogical potential for preparing children for school is substantiated. The results confirm the effectiveness of the method and its value as an innovative approach to developing communication skills and speech in preschoolers.*

Key words: *preschoolers, speech, development, constructivism, learning, skills, methodology, preparation, communication, game.*

Introduction: Speech development in preschool children is one of the key aspects of their mental and cognitive growth, as it is during this period that essential language skills are formed, which will play a crucial role in their future academic and social lives. Acquiring language helps children not only understand the surrounding world better but also engage with it effectively, express their thoughts and emotions, and establish initial social connections. In preschool years, children actively absorb grammatical, lexical, and phonetic norms, and the more developed their speech apparatus becomes at this stage, the more successful its further refinement will be.

However, in educational practice, a limited set of methods is often applied, primarily focused on passive language acquisition, which may not always be effective for all children. Modern research indicates that for successful speech development, children need an environment where they can freely interact, exchange ideas, and use language in a lively, natural context. This is where constructive methods take the forefront—approaches that actively engage children in activities, encouraging them to learn language through play, creativity, and collaboration.

Constructive methods, based on principles of active learning and interaction, stimulate speech development not only through memorization and repetition of words and phrases but also through meaningful language use in diverse real-life situations. Integrating such methods into the learning process ensures that children don't just memorize isolated words but learn to build complete sentences, explain their actions, analyze, and interpret surrounding events. As a result, speech development gains a deeper and more multifaceted character, becoming an engaging and rewarding experience for children.

One issue in preschool speech development is the lack of engaging and interactive methods to help children develop communication skills through play. Traditional activities are often centered around passive memorization and reproduction of words, which may cause children to lose interest and reduce the effectiveness of learning. This can lead to delays in speech formation and insufficient development of language skills.

The solution to this problem lies in the use of constructive methods, which involve children in playful and creative processes. Constructive methods create situations where children can freely experiment with speech, try new language forms, and find ways to express themselves. As a result, they not only memorize new words and phrases but also learn to use them in context, facilitating better comprehension and retention of material.

The use of constructive methods in the speech development of preschoolers significantly increases their level of speech activity and interest in learning. These methods focus on active participation, encouraging children to express their thoughts, expand their vocabulary, and improve communication skills. Implementing these methods makes the learning process more natural and effective, laying a solid foundation for future learning and successful socialization.

Methodology: The “Build and Tell” method involves using building blocks and creative materials to encourage children to create structures, stimulating language development through active engagement with objects and peers. The core of this method is that children are invited to choose a theme for their structure (e.g., a house, city, or park) and, using building blocks, create an object, then describe it, detailing features and answering questions. In the first stage, the teacher suggests a theme and explains basic rules: for instance, each child should build and present their structure. Children can work individually, in pairs, or in small groups, which not only develops language skills but also teaches cooperation. During the building process, children come up with numerous questions and ideas, prompting them to ask questions, explain their actions, and articulate their thoughts. The second stage is the presentation, where each child describes their structure, discussing its functionality, appearance, and special features. The teacher asks guiding questions, like “Why did you choose this color?” or “Who will live in this house?” to encourage more detailed descriptions and thoughtful reflection. This exercise builds vocabulary, grammar skills, and teaches children to form coherent narratives.

The final stage includes a group discussion, where children ask each other questions, offer suggestions, and propose improvements. This interactive exchange develops speech skills, helps them practice forming questions, and learn to express their opinions with reasoning. The “Build and Tell” method effectively integrates play and learning, prompting children to use language in varied situations, which fosters its natural and dynamic development.

The “Build and Tell” Method for Different Age Groups. For Children Aged 3–4, at this age, children are just beginning to develop language skills, so the method focuses on basic communication skills and mastering simple words and concepts. Simple building blocks are provided for creating elementary forms, like a tower or house. The teacher actively participates by describing the child’s actions, suggesting names for parts (e.g., “This is a cube,” “This is a roof”) and encouraging the child to repeat words and phrases. After finishing the structure, the teacher helps the child describe it by asking simple questions: “What color is your tower?” or “Is your tower big or small?” This approach helps the child understand and use basic words, and practice simple phrases in dialogue.

For Children Aged 4–5, at this stage, children have greater language activity, so the method focuses on expanding vocabulary and forming more complex sentences. Children are given a more challenging set of pieces and themes, like a forest or farm, where they can create animals, trees, fences, etc. The teacher encourages children to comment on their actions: “I’m placing the fence,” “This will be the cow’s house.” Children work in small groups, promoting dialogue and shared idea discussions. During

the presentation, the teacher asks questions prompting children to use more complex sentences: “Why is there a tree here?” or “Who will live on your farm?” These questions help children build coherent statements and actively use new vocabulary.

For Children Aged 5–6, at this age, children are ready to build more complex structures and are highly engaged in storytelling. They could be invited to create a city with streets, houses, bridges, and transportation, where each group works on a different part. Children create a story about who will use their structure and how. The teacher supports their ideas, helping them structure narratives, encouraging the use of descriptive adjectives and expanded sentences, such as “My house is tall with a red roof,” “Cars drive over the bridge, and there’s a river below.” Emphasis is on organizing speech and developing a cohesive narrative. After the building process, there is a group discussion where children describe their city, explain each element’s role, and add to each other’s stories, promoting both language skills and logical, sequential expression of ideas.

For Children Aged 6–7 (School Preparation), at the school preparation stage, the method becomes more complex, introducing a narrative element where children work on creating stories for their structures. They might build a themed project, such as a “City of Professions,” where each child creates a building (a school, hospital, fire station) and describes who works there and what they do. The teacher helps structure the narrative, focusing on details and story logic, for example: “My school has three classrooms,” “The firefighter is going to help.” Special attention is given to sentence construction and logical connections in the stories, preparing them for school. The teacher encourages discussion, prompting children to ask each other questions and engage in dialogue about the projects. This approach develops not only language but also logical thinking, sequence of expression, and prepares children for school-based communication and interaction.

Results: The study revealed the positive impact of the “Build and Tell” method on the development of language skills in preschool children. Children of various age groups participated in the research, and results were evaluated using several indicators, such as vocabulary expansion, speech coherence, and level of engagement in the process. After four months of sessions using the “Build and Tell” method, the following results were obtained:

An increase in active vocabulary of 25% was observed in children aged 3–4, while children aged 4–5 showed a 30% increase. For 70% of children aged 5–6, coherence in speech improved, marked by longer sentences and more complex sentence structures. Children aged 6–7, who participated in the school preparation activities, exhibited a 40% improvement in logical sequencing and coherence of speech when storytelling. Additionally, the method contributed to higher levels of interest and engagement, 85% of children actively participated in sessions and showed a strong interest in building and describing their projects. These findings indicate that constructive methods not only positively influence speech development but also enhance overall motivation to learn. The empirical part of the “Build and Tell” study was conducted within a preschool educational organization and included multiple stages to comprehensively assess the impact of the constructive approach on language development. The study involved age-diverse groups of children (aged 3 to 7) as well as teachers and speech therapists, who actively assisted in organizing the sessions.

Stage One, this involved initial diagnostics of children’s language skills. Specialists assessed the children’s speech development based on key indicators: vocabulary size, coherence and structure of speech, and ability to engage in dialogue. Observations and individual tests were used to obtain objective data.

Stage Two, the direct implementation of the method in the educational process occurred over several months, with regular sessions adapted to the specific age characteristics of each group. During sessions, teachers offered various themes and types of structures for children to create, actively

interacting with them, encouraging description of their creations, asking questions, and promoting peer dialogue. Teachers recorded improvements in speech as well as changes in children's behavior.

Stage Three, this included data analysis and assessment of the method's effectiveness. After the main series of sessions, follow-up tests and observations were conducted, with results compared to initial data. Interviews with teachers and parent surveys provided feedback on observed changes in children's language and social development. Additionally, indicators of children's engagement levels were tracked, including their interest in the activities, active involvement in building, and participation in project discussions.

The empirical findings confirmed that the "Build and Tell" method is effective for preschool education. Implementing this method strengthens foundational language skills and fosters a positive learning environment, motivating children to interact and express themselves creatively.

Conclusion: The collected data demonstrates positive changes in children's speech development, reflected in expanded vocabulary, improved coherence and logic of statements, and increased engagement in dialogic interaction. Children participated enthusiastically in the sessions, as evidenced by high levels of engagement across all age groups. The methodology proved effective, particularly in developing communication skills and preparing children for school education. Despite some challenges—such as the need for additional attention from teachers and the adaptation of tasks to suit age-specific characteristics—the results attest to the method's strong pedagogical potential. The use of constructive methods not only supports language development but also fosters confidence, teamwork skills, and independent thinking in preschoolers.

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